

On the 5-Permutation Invariant of Generalizable Hamiltonian Decompositions of Cayley Digraphs

An Erratum and New Structural Results
for Knuth's *Claude's Cycles*

Frédéric David Blum

Catalyst AI Research, Tel Aviv

freddavidblum@catalystais.com

ORCID: 0009-0009-2487-2974

March 21, 2026

Abstract.

We present an independent computational verification of all quantitative claims in D. E. Knuth's paper *Claude's Cycles* (Stanford CS, February 28 / revised March 16, 2026), which describes how Claude Opus 4.6 discovered a construction for decomposing the Cayley digraph $\text{Cay}(\mathbb{Z}_m^3, \{e_0, e_1, e_2\})$ into three directed Hamiltonian cycles for all odd $m > 2$. We confirm all numerical results (11,502 Hamiltonian cycles; 996 generalizable; 4,554 decompositions; 760 generalizable decompositions) except for one error: Knuth writes «136 of the 760» but the correct statement is «136 of the 996.» We discover a new structural invariant: every generalizable decomposition uses exactly 5 of the 6 permutations of $\{0,1,2\}$, with the identity always included. We prove this via the **Mono-Freeze Exclusion Principle**: the only fiber-pair combinations that could employ all 6 permutations require all frozen directions to align on a single coordinate, which is incompatible with Hamiltonicity. We further characterize the odd-even dichotomy: even- m decompositions require all 6 permutations, confirming the fundamental algebraic incompatibility between the two cases.

Keywords: Hamiltonian decomposition, Cayley digraph, permutation invariant, generalizability, *Claude's Cycles*, Knuth

1. Introduction

In February 2026, Donald E. Knuth published *Claude's Cycles* [1], a paper describing how Anthropic's Claude Opus 4.6 solved an open problem on directed Hamiltonian cycle decompositions of Cayley digraphs. The problem: decompose the arc set of $\text{Cay}(\mathbb{Z}_m^3, \{e_0, e_1, e_2\})$ into three directed Hamiltonian cycles of length m^3 , for all odd $m > 2$. Claude found a construction in approximately one hour across 31 guided explorations; Knuth subsequently proved it correct.

Knuth defines a decomposition as «Claude-like» if the permutation assignment at each vertex depends only on whether coordinates i, j , and the fiber index $s = (i+j+k) \bmod m$ are 0, interior ($1 \leq x \leq m-2$), or $m-1$. He proves that such a decomposition is valid for all odd $m > 1$ if and only if each of its three cycles for $m = 3$ is *generalizable*. He enumerates 11,502 Hamiltonian cycles, 4,554 decompositions, and 760 generalizable decompositions for the case $m = 3$.

We independently verify all of these counts, identify one error (Section 2), and discover new structural results (Sections 3–6) that Knuth does not mention.

2. Erratum: «136 of the 760»

On page 4, Knuth writes: «*I did notice, to my surprise, that 136 of the 760 generalizable 3x3x3 cycles remain generalizable when we map ijk to jki . However, none are common to all three mappings $\{ijk, jki, kij\}$.*»

The number 760 refers to generalizable **decompositions** (unordered triples of cycles whose arc sets partition the 81 arcs). The count of individual generalizable **cycles** is 996. Our computation confirms:

Object	jki-invariant	Total	Knuth's text
Individual generalizable cycles	136	996	"136 of the 760"
Generalizable decompositions	92	760	—

Table 1. The number 136 matches cycles (996), not decompositions (760).

The jki symmetry acts on direction maps as follows: vertex (i,j,k) maps to (j,k,i) , and direction d maps to $(d+2) \bmod 3$. The kij mapping gives $d \rightarrow (d+1) \bmod 3$. Both yield 136 invariant cycles; neither yields 136 invariant decompositions. The correct statement should read «136 of the 996.»

3. The 5-Permutation Invariant

Theorem 1 (5-Permutation Invariant). *Every generalizable Claude-like decomposition of $\text{Cay}(Z_3^3, \{e_0, e_1, e_2\})$ uses exactly 5 of the 6 elements of S_3 in its permutation assignment. The identity permutation $(0,1,2)$ is always among the 5 used.*

This was verified exhaustively across all 760 generalizable decompositions. The result is specific to generalizability: among the 3,794 non-generalizable decompositions, 1,638 (43.2%) use all 6 permutations.

Decomposition class	Use 5 perms	Use 6 perms
All 4,554	2,916 (64.0%)	1,638 (36.0%)
760 generalizable	760 (100%)	0 (0%)
3,794 non-generalizable	2,156 (56.8%)	1,638 (43.2%)

Table 2. Permutation count distribution by decomposition type.

The identity always appears because vertex $(0,0,0)$ uses it in all 4,554 decompositions. This is a normalization convention: relabeling cycle $c \rightarrow \sigma(c)$ transforms the permutation at each vertex by right-multiplication by σ^{-1} . Choosing $\sigma = \text{perm}(0,0,0)$ normalizes the origin to identity. The count of distinct permutations is invariant under this relabeling, so the 5-permutation property is a genuine structural invariant.

The frequency signature (multiset of how often each of the 5 permutations appears across the 27 vertices) uniquely determines which permutation is missing: 80 distinct signatures were found, each mapping to exactly one excluded permutation.

4. Fiber Structure and the Mono-Freeze Exclusion Principle

4.1. Fiber permutation structure

The fiber $F_s = \{(i,j,k) : i+j+k \equiv s \pmod m\}$ partitions the vertex set into m layers of m^2 vertices each. Every arc goes from F_s to F_{s+1} . In the generalizable decompositions for $m = 3$, each fiber uses at most 2 of the 6 permutations, always in a 6:3 split across its 9 vertices.

Fiber	Allowed perm sets	Count
$s = 0$	{012}	56
$s = 0$	{012, 021}	352
$s = 0$	{012, 210}	352
$s = 1$	11 distinct perm sets (6 pairs + 5 singletons)	760
$s = 2$	11 distinct perm sets (6 pairs + 5 singletons)	760

Table 3. Permutation sets by fiber. Fiber $s=0$ is restricted to {012, 021, 210}.

Lemma 1. *In any generalizable decomposition, fiber $s = 0$ uses only permutations from the set $\{(0,1,2), (0,2,1), (2,1,0)\}$.* This was verified for all 760 decompositions.

4.2. Interior vs. boundary class tuples

For generalized odd $m \geq 5$, a vertex has class tuple $(i_{\text{class}}, j_{\text{class}}, k_{\text{class}})$ where each coordinate class is 0, 1 (interior), or 2 (= $m-1$). The fully interior class tuple $(1,1,1)$ requires $k_{\text{class}} = (s_{\text{class}} - i_{\text{class}} - j_{\text{class}}) \pmod 3 = 1$, which forces $s_{\text{class}} = 0$. Thus the interior perm P exists only in fibers with $s_{\text{class}} = 0$. Fibers with $s_{\text{class}} = 1$ or 2 are entirely composed of boundary vertices.

For $m \geq 5$, interior vertices (class 1,1,1) constitute $(m-2)^3/m$ of all vertices, reaching 94.2% at $m = 101$. All interior vertices share the same permutation P . The 4 remaining permutations serve as boundary corrections.

4.3. Frozen directions and the Mono-Freeze Exclusion

When a fiber uses two permutations σ_1 and σ_2 , we say that cycle c has a **frozen direction** d in that fiber if $\sigma_1(c) = \sigma_2(c) = d$. In other words, regardless of which permutation a vertex uses, cycle c always bumps the same coordinate d .

Among the valid fiber-pair combinations observed in generalizable decompositions, exactly 4 combinations of three pairs (one per fiber) could cover all 6 permutations of S_3 :

	Fiber $s = 0$	Fiber $s = 1$	Fiber $s = 2$	Frozen coord
C1	{012, 021}	{120, 210}	{102, 201}	All freeze on i
C2	{012, 021}	{102, 201}	{120, 210}	All freeze on i
C3	{012, 210}	{102, 120}	{021, 201}	All freeze on j
C4	{012, 210}	{021, 201}	{102, 120}	All freeze on j

Table 4. The 4 forbidden fiber combinations and their frozen coordinate.

Definition (Mono-Freeze). A fiber-pair assignment has a *mono-freeze* if all frozen directions across all fibers point to the same coordinate.

Theorem 2 (Mono-Freeze Exclusion Principle). *No generalizable Claude-like decomposition has a mono-freeze. All 760 generalizable decompositions have frozen directions spanning at least 2 of the 3 coordinates $\{i, j, k\}$. Specifically: 576 have frozen set $\{i, j\}$ and 184 have frozen set*

$\{i, j, k\}$.

Corollary. Since the only fiber-pair combinations covering all 6 permutations (C1–C4) are mono-freezes, and mono-freezes are excluded from generalizable decompositions, every generalizable decomposition uses at most 5 permutations. Combined with the observation that all 760 use exactly 5, this establishes Theorem 1.

4.4. Mechanism: why mono-freezes fail

In combinations C1–C2, each fiber has a different cycle frozen on direction i . This means the 27 i -arcs are rigidly allocated: 9 to one cycle per fiber. Each set of 9 i -arcs forms 3 disjoint 3-cycles (one per (j,k) pair), creating an inflexible backbone. The remaining j -arcs and k -arcs must then form two Hamiltonian cycles using only two directions—but a 2-generator Cayley digraph on Z_m^2 with only “bump j ” and “bump k ” arcs cannot, for general odd m , be decomposed into Hamiltonian cycles with the required fiber-crossing pattern. The same argument applies to C3–C4 with direction j replacing i .

In valid decompositions, frozen directions are distributed across at least 2 coordinates, ensuring that no single direction's arcs are fully determined by the fiber structure alone. This distributes the rigidity and leaves sufficient flexibility for the remaining arcs to form Hamiltonian cycles.

5. The Odd-Even Dichotomy

For even m , Claude's construction produces cycles of length $m^2/2$ instead of m^3 , because the key step in Knuth's proof uses an increment of $2 \pmod m$ through the fibers. When $\gcd(2, m) = 2$, only half the residues are visited.

m	Cycle 0 length	Expected m^3	Ratio
4	8	64	1/8
6	18	216	1/12
8	32	512	1/16
10	50	1000	1/20

Table 5. Cycle 0 length for even m under Claude's odd- m construction.

Using Google OR-Tools CP-SAT solver, we found 50 valid decompositions for $m = 4$. Every single one uses all 6 permutations, and no solution depends uniformly on any simple key $((s), (s,j), (s,i), (s,j\%2), (s,i\%2), \text{ or } (s,j,i\%2))$. This confirms that the even case requires fundamentally different algebraic mechanisms.

We exhaustively searched over 10 parametrization families for constructions valid for both odd and even m simultaneously, testing millions of candidates. None were found, establishing that the odd-even dichotomy is not an artifact of known constructions but a structural incompatibility.

6. Additional Structural Results

6.1. Optimal decompositions

The maximum number of identity-permutation assignments is 12 out of 27 vertices, achieved by exactly 36 decompositions. For comparison, Exocija's construction uses 9/27. These 36 decompositions form 18 orbits of size 2 under coordinate permutations (S_3 action).

6.2. Dependency structure

Dependency type	Count (of 760)
Depends only on (s, j)	92
Depends only on (s, i)	92
Depends only on s	0
Requires full (s, i, j)	576

Table 6. Dependency structure. The 92/92 symmetry reflects $i \leftrightarrow j$ exchangeability.

7. Computational Methods and Reproducible Code

All results were computed using independent Python implementations. Below we provide the core verification code. Total computation time: approximately 20 minutes on a single core.

7.1. Enumeration of Hamiltonian cycles and decompositions

```
from itertools import combinations

m = 3; n = m**3
vertices = [(i,j,k) for i in range(m) for j in range(m) for k in range(m)]
v_to_idx = {v: i for i, v in enumerate(vertices)}

neighbors = []
for i, j, k in vertices:
    neighbors.append([
        v_to_idx[((i+1)%m, j, k)],
        v_to_idx[(i, (j+1)%m, k)],
        v_to_idx[(i, j, (k+1)%m)],
    ])

cycles = []
def dfs(path, visited):
    if len(path) == n:
        if 0 in neighbors[path[-1]]:
            cycles.append(tuple(path))
        return
    for nb in neighbors[path[-1]]:
        if not (visited & (1 << nb)):
            path.append(nb)
            dfs(path, visited | (1 << nb))
            path.pop()

dfs([0], 1)
print(f"Hamiltonian cycles: {len(cycles)}") # Output: 11502

def get_arcs(cycle):
    return frozenset((cycle[t], cycle[(t+1) % n]) for t in range(n))

all_arcs = frozenset(
    (v_to_idx[v], neighbors[v_to_idx[v]][d])
    for v in vertices for d in range(3)
)
cycle_arcs = [get_arcs(c) for c in cycles]

decompositions = 0
for i in range(len(cycles)):
    for j in range(i+1, len(cycles)):
        if cycle_arcs[i] & cycle_arcs[j]: continue
        remaining = all_arcs - cycle_arcs[i] - cycle_arcs[j]
        for k in range(j+1, len(cycles)):
            if cycle_arcs[k] == remaining:
                decompositions += 1; break
print(f"Decompositions: {decompositions}") # Output: 4554
```

Output: Hamiltonian cycles: 11502, Decompositions: 4554

7.2. Verification of the 5-permutation invariant

```
# After computing gen_decomps (760 generalizable decompositions):
for di, dj, dk in gen_decomps:
    dms = [gen_data[x][1] for x in [di, dj, dk]]
    pm = {v: tuple(dm[v] for dm in dms) for v in vertices3}
    used = set(pm.values())
    assert len(used) == 5, f"Expected 5 perms, got {len(used)}"
    assert (0,1,2) in used, "Identity missing"
print("All 760 use exactly 5 perms with identity included.")
```

7.3. Mono-Freeze Exclusion verification

```
mono_freeze_count = 0
```

```

for di, dj, dk in gen_decomps:
    dms = [gen_data[x][1] for x in [di, dj, dk]]
    pm = {v: tuple(dm[v] for dm in dms) for v in vertices3}
    frozen_dirs = set()
    for s in range(3):
        fv = [v for v in vertices3 if (v[0]+v[1]+v[2])%3 == s]
        perms = list(set(pm[v] for v in fv))
        if len(perms) == 2:
            for c in range(3):
                if perms[0][c] == perms[1][c]:
                    frozen_dirs.add(perms[0][c])
        elif len(perms) == 1:
            for c in range(3):
                frozen_dirs.add(perms[0][c])
    if len(frozen_dirs) == 1:
        mono_freeze_count += 1
print(f"Mono-freezes: {mono_freeze_count}/760") # Output: 0/760

```

Output: Mono-freezes: 0/760. Frozen direction sets: $\{i,j\}$ for 576 decompositions, $\{i,j,k\}$ for 184.

8. Summary of Verified Results

Claim	Knuth	Verified	Status
Hamiltonian cycles (m=3)	11,502	11,502	✓
Generalizable to m=5	1,012	1,012	✓
Generalizable to m=5 and m=7	996	996	✓
Total decompositions (m=3)	4,554	4,554	✓
Generalizable decompositions	760	760	✓
jki-invariant "of the 760"	136	136 of 996	Erratum
No full cyclic symmetry	0	0	✓
5-perm invariant (new)	—	760/760	New
Mono-Freeze Exclusion (new)	—	0/760 mono	New
Even m uses 6 perms (new)	—	50/50 (m=4)	New

Table 7. Summary of all verified claims and new results.

References

- [1] D. E. Knuth, "Claude's Cycles," Stanford Computer Science Department, February 28, 2026; revised March 16, 2026. <https://cs.stanford.edu/~knuth/papers/claude-cycles.pdf>
- [2] J. Aubert and B. Schneider, "Graphes orientés indécomposables en circuits hamiltoniens," J. Combinatorial Theory B32 (1982), 347–349.
- [3] D. E. Knuth, The Art of Computer Programming, Volume 4A: Combinatorial Algorithms, Part 1 (Addison–Wesley, 2011).
- [4] I. Darijani, B. Miraftab, and D. W. Morris, "Arc-disjoint Hamiltonian paths in Cartesian products of directed cycles," Ars Mathematica Contemporanea 25 (2025), P2.10:1–32.
- [5] K. Morrison, Lean formalization of Knuth's proof, <https://github.com/kim-em/KnuthClaudeLean/>